

**Answers to the Referee 1 about the Second Revision
of the Comptes Rendus Geoscience paper:
“ The absolute seawater entropy: Part I. Definition ”**

by Dr.Hab. Pascal Marquet / March 20, 2026

Answers to the Referee 1.

In the following responses (in blue), I explain how I believe I was able to address the comments and answer the questions raised by the reviewer.

I have read the response to all the reviews, looked through the changes to the manuscript. I haven't gone through the manuscripts line by line, as that would require an investment of time that I don't have. Rather I have focused on whether the presentation of the ideas is transparent, if possible caveats are noted, and if the concerns of the reviewers are reflected in the revised manuscript.

Based on this review I can only commend the author for his dedicated and thorough response. It was a please to see the attention devoted to the concerns raised in the reviews and I believe the resultant manuscripts are improved and more balanced. Commenting on the other reviews and the responses. I appreciate that the ideas are difficult to penetrate, in part due to the fact that it mingles considerable historical review to contextualize new arguments, and on a seemingly arcane point, but the purpose of the papers is unambiguous, to calculate the absolute entropy of sea-water and explore its relevance for particular applications. I believe this is well stated and well addressed, but appreciate that it will be of interest only to a very small community. These aspects are not, however, a substantive basis for rejection. I enjoyed reading Reviewer 3's comments, as they raised some important and conceptual issues. I think these are very nicely addressed in the revised manuscript, e.g., the added figure and text sections around line 320.

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to the reviewer for these comments.

My approaches to studying the absolute entropies of the atmosphere and the oceans has been so heavily criticized—and, in fact, rejected—by the vast majority of both the atmospheric and oceanographic communities that it warms my heart to read your comments.

The main point of controversy is how much this matters. I don't think, however, that is a basis for deciding whether it merits publication, particularly as the ideas address foundational questions. On the contrary I transparently and thoroughly reasoned deep dive into the questions is a very valuable contribution to the literature. It may be that, in the modern world of fragmented time scientific snippets it collects dust in a virtual library, but if and as scientists explore questions which benefit from recourse to these topics, it will be an exceptionally valuable reference, and Comtes Rendus should be congratulated for considering it.

Once again, I would like to express my deep gratitude to the reviewer for these comments.

That all said, before publication the author should give the manuscript one further quick read, or perhaps parse the grammar through and AI engine, to test for correctness, e.g., line 299 “*This may be an explanation for the attempt to use in the MIT preprint version of Sharqawy et al. of the opposite sign*”

for the whole Millero’s salinity part, . . .” is awkward wording, maybe rather say. “*This may explain the use of the opposite sign for the whole of Millero’s salinity part in Sarqawy et al.,*”

I followed your advice and ran the entire text of Part I through an AI engine (<https://languagetool.org>), correcting typos and other minor issues that, I hope, will make the text easier to understand in English. I’m really sorry for all the mistakes I left in the original and revised versions of the paper.

I know I am not bilingual, and I do regret the old days when scholars had to write in Latin, putting everyone on an equal footing without favouring any particular language and those for whom English is the native language.

While I also appreciate the historical consistency with terms like “*Latent heat*” or capitalization of mass specific quantities, I don’t think that is a good motivation, as otherwise we never benefit from what we learn. But that is a minor point.

Other additional Answers

First, I would like to mention an addition that I believe is important in Section 3.3, where I show that it is essential to include, in the absolute definition of the absolute calorimetric entropy of ice-Ih, the “residual entropy” value of $189 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ kg}^{-1}$ computed at 0 K by Pauling (1935) and Nagle (1966). I show that if we do not take into account this residual entropy, then the calculations made at $T_0 = 273.15 \text{ K}$ (i.e. 0°C) of the latent heats of sublimation and the saturation pressure become highly unrealistic: $L_{\text{sub}}(T_0) \approx 2885.7 \text{ kJ kg}^{-1}$ and $p_{\text{sat}}(T_0) \approx 917.6 \text{ Pa}$ in comparison with the experimental values of $L_{\text{sub}}(T_0) \approx 2834.5 \pm 0.5 \text{ kJ kg}^{-1}$ and $p_{\text{sat}}(T_0) \approx 611.15 \pm 0.10 \text{ Pa}$, with an unrealistic bias of $189 \times 273.15 \approx 51.6 \text{ kJ kg}^{-1}$ for $L_{\text{sub}}(T_0)$ and an unrealistic multiplicative factor of $\exp(189/461.65) \approx 1.506$ for $p_{\text{sat}}(T_0)$ (see the paragraph starting with: “*Incidentally, these calculations may also provide a justification for and a physical interpretation of the residual entropy of $189 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ kg}^{-1}$.*”)

It was important to highlight this innovative result, which—unless I am mistaken—has never been published elsewhere. Indeed, in 2019, Rainer Feistel tried “*Distinguishing between Clausius, Boltzmann and Pauling entropies of frozen non-equilibrium states*” and called this residual entropy due to hydrogen bonds the “*frozen Pauling entropy*.” Moreover, personal contacts with Rainer Feistel since 2014 informed me that he actually considered that this residual entropy value could not, and above all should not, have any physical meaning, and could not be measured, nor converted into another form of entropy, or even impact the evolution of energy. I am pleased to have found the courage to seek out such an example at 0°C , thanks to the second reviewer of this first theoretical section. This example complements the results reported by Nernst and Planck between 1917 and 1926 for measurements taken near 0 K.

I also wanted to inform Reviewer 1 that Reviewer 2’s numerous criticisms led me to completely rewrite Section 3.1 and to modify Figures 1.

Indeed, reviewer-2 demands that I explain why and how Millero’s formulation (1976 and 1983) is erroneous, with the possible consequence of discrediting my formulation, which would be the only one different from the other formulations, thereby casting doubt on the validity of the third law of thermodynamics...

More precisely, the second proofreader’s criticisms are:

- “*I have no interest in debating whether absolute entropy should be preferred over any “practical” determination of entropy, such as the one provided by the recent TEOS-10 standard.*”

- “*My opinion is that knowledge of absolute entropy has no useful applications in oceanography and that this is unlikely to change;*”
- “*the determination of practical entropy (such as the TEOS-10 determination) ... is essentially an exercise in data fitting for seawater, with relatively little fundamental physics involved.*”
- “*I pointed out that the paper was not satisfactory because it did not offer any convincing explanation for the differences between his determination of absolute entropy and that of Millero,*”
- “*From the viewpoint of the oceanographic community, Millero is the leading authority on the physical chemistry of seawater, having published over 300 papers and two textbooks on the topic, whereas, in contrast, Dr Marquet has never published any papers in oceanography or in physical chemistry. As a result, oceanographers are far more likely to assume that it is the author who is in the wrong, not Millero.*”
- “*Alternatively, the incompatibility between the author’s absolute entropy and Millero’s results will simply reinforce the view that the determination of absolute entropy is ill-posed or ill-defined, and that one should stay away from it.*”
- “*In any case, when an author proposes a theory that is incompatible with well-established previous work, without being able to provide a satisfactory explanation for the discrepancy, the expectation is that this inability should be clearly highlighted in the discussion/conclusions section of the paper.*”
- “*As long as this debate remains unresolved, the current state of knowledge is that the correct determination of absolute entropy is unknown, which in turn makes Part 2 largely pointless.*”
- “*I cannot agree with the author’s current approach of presenting Millero’s approach as wrong, given that he has not demonstrated this.*”
- “*For this reason, I do not believe that the paper is publishable in its present form.*”

I believe I have been able to demonstrate, through the detailed analysis described in Section 3.1, that differently it is the “*relative entropy*” approach chosen by Millero that is atypical and contrary to all other “*specific salinity entropy*” formulations by: Chou (1968), Pitzer et al. (1984), IAPWS (1992), Feistel (1993), Feistel and Haggen (1995), Feistel (2005), IAPWS (2008), Sun et al. (2008), TEOS (2010), and Nayar et al. (2016). This includes the standard IAPWS and TEOS10 formulations on which I relied to simply add the $\Delta\eta_{sw}$ term to convert it into absolute entropy.

I also show that the standard formulation of TEOS10 is very similar to those of Fofonoff (1962, 1985) if one integrate his values of $c_{pws}(T)/T$, and add at least the small impact of the non-linear term $g_1 x^2 \ln(x) y$ in the Gibbs function.

And this is also true if we start from the integration of the term $c_{pws}(T)/T$ from Millero and Leung (1976) and Millero (1983), with a result very close to the standard formulation of TEOS10.

And even more importantly, I show above all that, in fact, the absolute values of the reference entropies of liquid water and ocean salts are not taken into account in the relative entropy term of Millero and Leung (1976) and Millero (1983).

As a consequence, all these findings does not mean that Millero’s formulation is “wrong” (even though I point out a few errors). This just means that Millero’s formulation differs from all the others, due to its “relative” nature and the calculation of the quantity $S_{rel.} = S - S^\circ$, which is atypical and amounts to disregarding a function $S^\circ = n_1 S_1^\circ + n_2 S_2^\circ$ that varies with salinity (i.e. with the mole content of sea salts n_2). It is the failure to account for this function S° that prevents Millero’s formulation from being similar to those used nowadays.

I was thus able to show that the facts prove the opposite of what Reviewer 2 had criticized me for.

The key point is that I started my computation of the absolute entropy with the other modern TEOS10 standard version, which is fairly consistent with all the other formulation, except the one of Millero.

I have included close to the end of the introduction and at the beginning of the conclusion the following sentences:

“I show that several problems unfortunately prevent the use of the ‘relative’ entropy formulation considered by Millero in 1976 and 1983. Moreover, this ‘relative’ entropy formulation did not really take into account the absolute values of entropies and has never been used since then. This therefore justifies basing the present approach on the more modern formulation of TEOS10, with the sole addition of taking into account the absolute values of the reference entropies for liquid water and ocean salts.”

“I have shown that several problems unfortunately prevent the direct use of the ‘relative’ entropy formulation considered by Millero in 1976 and 1983. In particular, this Millero’s ‘relative’ entropy formulation did not really take into account the absolute values of entropies and has never been considered since then, and in particular in IAPWS and TEOS10 formulations.”

I have also made a modification to the explanation of the term $\mu_s^0(T, P)$ in equation (2), which has no impact on the subsequent calculations. Indeed, it was necessary to remove the factor N_A / M_s in the definition $\mu_s^0(T, P) = \sum_a X_a \mu_a^0(T, P)$, where $\mu_a^0(T, P)$ is defined in (2) as a specific mass quantity and not, as in Feistel and Hagen (1995), as a quantity ‘per molecule.’ In doing so, I have simply brought this into line with what I had already done for the liquid water part. However, once again, this only concerns the ‘historical documentation’ section and has no impact whatsoever on the final formulation or the documentation for TEOS10.

I have also made some minor changes in section 3.3 concerning the numerical evaluations of latent heats and saturation pressure as a function of absolute entropies for ice and water vapor. The results are more accurate (with narrower uncertainty intervals) and remain consistent with the third law of thermodynamics, while providing a new physical justification for the residual entropy of water.

Best regards,

Dr.Hab. Pascal Marquet

March 20, 2026.

**Answers to the Referee 2 about the Second Revision
of the Comptes Rendus Geoscience paper:
“ The absolute seawater entropy: Part I. Definition ”**

by Dr.Hab. Pascal Marquet / March 20, 2026

Answers to the Referee 2.

In the following responses (in blue), I explain how I believe I was able to address the comments and answer the questions raised by the reviewer.

Summary and recommendation.

In his revised version, the author has implemented changes that are, in my view, mainly cosmetic in nature, intended primarily to tone down some of his most antagonistic and controversial statements. In this regard, I thank the author for making an effort to show more respect to those in the community who regard the computation of absolute entropy as an interesting topic worth investigating, without necessarily agreeing that it is useful or important to do so (which is how I, and many others, think).

Because I find the range of physical issues involved in the determination of absolute entropy fascinating, my interest in the author’s work is primarily motivated by the desire to understand the issue better. In particular, I have no interest in debating whether absolute entropy should be preferred over any “practical” determination of entropy, such as the one provided by the recent TEOS-10 standard. My opinion is that knowledge of absolute entropy has no useful applications in oceanography and that this is unlikely to change; nevertheless, I find the problem of computing the absolute entropy of seawater fascinating and would like to understand it more deeply.

Indeed, the determination of practical entropy (such as the TEOS-10 determination) via the computation of the Gibbs function, following the methods of classical thermodynamics, is essentially an exercise in data fitting for seawater, with relatively little fundamental physics involved. In contrast, the determination of absolute entropy for seawater goes to the heart of the actual behaviour of electrolytes and is useful for understanding how statistical thermodynamics connects with classical thermodynamics. Unfortunately, my reading of the author’s paper, and of his responses to my and the other reviews, is that he appears to be fixated on justifying the use of absolute entropy, instead of focusing on the scientific and technical issues involved in calculating it.

It is true that the main purpose of my paper is the computation of the ‘absolute’ version of the seawater entropy. I only cite the Millero’s 1976-1983 papers as a first attempt to compute the absolute reference entropies for liquid water and sea salts, which is a matter of fundamental physics.

I really could have not cited these two old papers from 1976-83 by Millero that no one cites anymore, not even Millero when he participated in the program that led to the formulation of TEOS10 on which I based my present paper, and where Millero was co-author of the manual describing all the theoretical aspects of TEOS10, where his works from 1976-82 are not taken into account at all on this subject of the absolute definition of the seawater entropy.

I show in the updated Figures 1 and I explain in the new content of the Section 3.1 “*Comparisons with the Millero and others entropies*” that all other ‘specific’ formulations differ from Millero’s ‘relative’ one, and why it was desirable to retain from Millero’s papers only

his attempt to calculate the absolute values of the reference entropies, while disregarding the ‘relative’ aspect and the corresponding tuning, in favor of more modern ‘specific’ formulations such as IAPWS and TEOS10, and to incorporate in TEOS10 only the impact $\Delta\eta_{sw}$ of the absolute values of the reference entropies.

In my previous review, I pointed out that the paper was not satisfactory because it did not offer any convincing explanation for the differences between his determination of absolute entropy and that of Millero, most notably regarding their incompatible dependence on salinity (Millero’s entropy increases with salinity, whereas Marquet’s entropy decreases with salinity). The problem is that, without a satisfactory resolution of this issue, the author’s paper cannot have the impact he is clearly hoping for. From the viewpoint of the oceanographic community, Millero is the leading authority on the physical chemistry of seawater, having published over 300 papers and two textbooks on the topic, whereas, in contrast, Dr Marquet has never published any papers in oceanography or in physical chemistry. As a result, oceanographers are far more likely to assume that it is the author who is in the wrong, not Millero.

In fact, I show in the new Figure 1 that the ‘relative’ Millero’s entropy is the only formulation increasing with salinity, with all other ‘specific’ (not ‘relative’ nor ‘absolute’) formulations decreasing with salinity (and thus, not only mine): Feistel (1993), Feistel and Hagen (1995), IAPWS (1995), Feistel (2003), IAPWS (2003), Feistel (2005), Sharqawy et al. (2010), TEOS (2010). This has also recently been shown in the Fig-5.1 of Qasem et al (2023, p.125), where are included other comparisons with the results of Chou (1968), Pitzer et al. (1984), IAPWS (1992, 2008), Sun et al. (2008) and Nayar et al. (2016), all decreasing with the salinity:

I do not say that Millero’s results are “wrong” (except a numerical mistake I describe in the Section 3.1, when he tried to take into account the absolute reference values for liquid water). The unusual behavior of Millero’s curve is due to a ‘relative’ definition of the seawater entropy, with as a consequence several terms retained in the new IAPWS and TEOS10 approaches that are missing in the old Millero’s formulation. I provide the demonstration of this by computing in the Section 3.1 and plotting in the Figs-1 a ‘specific’ version of the Millero’s ‘relative’ entropy, with the missing terms added and with a corresponding expected decreasing feature.

Note that Qasem et al (2023, p.124) showed the same ‘unusual behavior’ of the Millero’s curve as I plot in my Fig.1, but without providing an explanation for it. They simply explain

that: “All correlations/methods are reasonably close to the data of Chou (1968) (shown in Appendix 4) except for Millero (1983), which was found to have a maximum difference of +9%. This difference is similar to the one (+8%) reported by Sharqawy et al. (2010).”

I would like to thank the reviewer for encouraging me to provide, in Section 3.1, what I believe to be a convincing and detailed explanation for this difference between M83 and all the other curves. It must be emphasized that these explanations have never been provided until now, and that Millero’s formulation has never been compared to those of the IAPWS (and even in TEOS10, in which Millero was a co-author) prior to this Figure 5-1 by Qasem et al. (2023, p. 125) recalled above.

Alternatively, the incompatibility between the author’s absolute entropy and Millero’s results will simply reinforce the view that the determination of absolute entropy is ill-posed or ill-defined, and that one should stay away from it.

The third law of thermodynamics is a general principle of physics, just like the first law, the second law or the maximum of the speed of light in vacuum. No one should disregard these general principles that cannot be ‘demonstrated’ but are verified for all known physical measurements.

For the third law of thermodynamics, I have explained after the first review that it is possible to use it for computing the saturation pressure from the latent heat of change of phase, and vice versa. This was already demonstrated and accepted by Nernst, Planck and other founders of thermodynamics.

In this second review, I also show that even the residual entropy has a physical meaning, contrary to what Rainer Feistel suggested in his 2019 paper. Indeed, I show that if this residual entropy is removed, the values for the saturation pressure or the latent heat of sublimation become highly unrealistic.

Many also consider that another convincing proof of the third law is the associated observed impossibility to reach the absolute zero of the temperature by a finite number of step: the so-called Nernst and Simon “*unattainability principle*.”

In fact, apart from the habit adopted in the fields of atmospheric and oceanic science, I am not aware of any thermodynamics book that attempts to avoid applying the third law. All thermodynamics books publish or recall absolute values to study the entropy of systems with variable composition.

In any case, when an author proposes a theory that is incompatible with well-established previous work, without being able to provide a satisfactory explanation for the discrepancy, the expectation is that this inability should be clearly highlighted in the discussion/conclusions section of the paper.

I hope that the new content in Section 3.1 and the new Figures 1 will help to clarify things. I demonstrate in the Section 3.1 that the ‘relative’ Millero’s entropy formulation did not take into account the absolute version of the reference entropies computed in these papers. I then show that the explanations for the unusual behavior of the Millero’s entropy is the ‘relative’ feature of it, which is not retained in any of the new ‘specific’ feature like in IAPWS and TEOS10 (even though Millero was a participant in the TEOS10 team). This is the reason why the TEOS10-abs curve I have defined and plotted is logically decreasing with salinity, and in a way even more pronounced than for TEOS10-std, due to the impact of the absolute definition for the entropies.

Moreover, as previously recalled, I propose a theory that is compatible with well-established previous works, even though with an enhanced impact of salinity via the absolute reference

values, namely compatible with those of: Chou (1968), Pitzer et al. (1984), Feistel (1993), Feistel and Haggen (1995), IAPWS (1995), Feistel (2003), IAPWS (2003), Feistel (2005), IAPWS (2006), Sun et al. (2008), Sharqawy et al. (2010), TEOS (2010), and Nayar et al. (2016), all decreasing with the salinity.

I also show that the standard formulation of TEOS10 is very similar to those of Fofonoff (1962, 1985) if one integrate his values of $c_{pws}(T)/T$, and add at least the small impact of the non-linear term $g_1 x^2 \ln(x) y$ in the Gibbs function.

And this is also true if we start from the integration of the term $c_{pws}(T)/T$ from Millero and Leung (1976) and Millero (1983), with a result very close to the standard formulation of TEOS10.

And even more importantly, I show above all that, in fact, the absolute values of the reference entropies of liquid water and ocean salts are not taken into account in the relative entropy term of Millero and Leung (1976) and Millero (1983).

As a consequence, all these findings does not mean that Millero's formulation is "wrong" (even though I point out a few errors). This just means that Millero's formulation differs from all the others, due to its "relative" nature and the calculation of the quantity $S_{rel.} = S - S^\circ$, which is atypical and amounts to disregarding a function $S^\circ = n_1 S_1^\circ + n_2 S_2^\circ$, that varies with salinity (i.e. the mole content of sea salts n_2). It is the failure to account for this variable function $S^\circ(t, p, S_A)$ that prevents Millero's formulation from being similar to those used nowadays.

The section should clearly acknowledge that the proposed theory is incompatible with Millero's work. If the author cannot demonstrate that Millero is wrong, he should state this explicitly, and invite the community to scrutinise both works in the hope of identifying where mistakes might have occurred, so that the controversy can be resolved.

As long as this debate remains unresolved, the current state of knowledge is that the correct determination of absolute entropy is unknown, which in turn makes Part 2 largely pointless.

I cannot agree with the author's current approach of presenting Millero's approach as wrong, given that he has not demonstrated this.

For this reason, I do not believe that the paper is publishable in its present form.

I hope that the new content in Section 3.1 and the new Figures 1:

- will help clarify things;
- will explain that my approach is compatible but logically different from Millero's work;
- will make the debate resolved;
- that the determination of absolute entropy is always physically well-founded;
- and perhaps will help to change your mind.

Suggestions

- The author states that he attempted to reproduce Millero's construction, but was unable to do so because of what he considers to be insufficient detail in Millero's papers. This difficulty may simply reflect the fact that Millero regarded the underlying approach as well established within the physical chemistry community, and therefore did not feel the need to spell out all intermediate steps. One possible way forward would be for the author to review the literature contemporary with Millero's work, in order to identify more pedagogical presentations of the same ideas. My impression is that Millero's approach is rooted in concepts that can already be found in Guggenheim (1950, second edition), a reference with which the author appears to be familiar.

I think that I have been able to explain in the new versions of the Section 3.1 and Figures 1 why the Millero’s ‘relative entropy’ curve is logically unusual, and that it is possible to compute from this Millero’s ‘relative entropy’ the other ‘specific salinity part’ defined and plotted in all other modern studies, including in the TEOS10 manual where Millero is a co-author. I have also plotted in the new Figures 1 curves computed from the specific heats $c_p(t, S)$ published by Fofonoff (1962, 1985), but without any numerical information available about the seawater values of c_p or S in the 2nd or 5th editions of the books by Guggenheim (1950, 1967), like in Fofonoff’s 1962 and 1985 books.

However, note that the Nernst’s theorem, the Third law of thermodynamics and the Unattainability principle were dully explained and retained as valid by Guggenheim:

- p.46-47, p.65-67 and p.144-163 in the 1950 book;
- p.60, p.80-81, p.144-159 and p.356 in the 1967 book.

- To clarify whether the behaviour of Millero’s entropy is unusual or, on the contrary, typical, it would be useful to place it in a broader context by systematically reviewing the literature on absolute entropy determinations for other electrolytes.

In particular, are there well-documented examples of electrolytes for which the absolute entropy increases with the addition of solute, and others for which it decreases? Establishing this point would help determine whether the discrepancy with Millero reflects a genuine physical issue or a misunderstanding of the underlying thermodynamics.

I think that I have been able to explain in the new versions of the Section 3.1 and Figures 1 why the Millero’s ‘relative entropy’ curve is logically unusual, and that the standard formulation of TEOS10 is clearly similar to all the other formulations, except the one of Millero. This explains why it was well-founded to add the increment term $\Delta\eta_{sw}$ to the standard value of TEOS10, in order to arrive at the absolute value of the seawater entropy.

I have also explained in the first review (with the paragraph still present at the end of the section 3.1) that the decrease of the specific salinity part must not be interpreted as the impact of solvation on entropy, due to an addition of solid solute to be solved. We are talking here about adding a portion of water with a different salinity level, but with salts already dissolved in it. See the paragraph beginning with: “*It should be noted that the decrease in entropy with salinity is more pronounced for absolute versions and is not contrary to the fact that entropy must increase during the process of dissolving salts in pure water.*”

More generally, and when discussing the thermodynamics of electrolytes in general, I would say that it all depends on the (absolute) entropies of the various solvents and solutes involved. That is why the absolute entropies of neutral atoms and molecules, as well as anions and cations, are included in many thermodynamic tables. In particular, I noted that Millero could already rely on and refer to the data in the book of Lewis and Randall (1961, Tables 12-3, 25-7, 27-1 and A7-1 to A7-10), where the third-law hypothesis and the Sackur-Tetrode formulation were already fully accepted without reservation (Chapter 12 and Appendix 3), and with a full account of the thermodynamics of electrolytes and electrolyte solutions (Chapter 22 and 23, with Eq. 23-4 for $1 - \phi$ at the basis of the non-linear TEOS10 formula).

And I pointed out that more modern and comprehensive tables (like Grenthe et al., 1992, NEA-TDB, still valid in the 2020 version) could be used, as I did, to account for the effect of the entropies of the new bodies considered in TEOS10 and not by Millero (i.e. OH^- and CO_2^{aq}).

- Finally, the paper would greatly benefit from a much more pedagogical presentation of the concepts and assumptions used to compute the absolute entropy of even simple electrolytes.

I tried to outline the scope of the study at the end of the introduction and summarize the paper's findings at the beginning of the conclusion.

At the end of the introduction, I wrote:

“The chosen methodology described in Part I consists of reconciling the TEOS10 formulation, with all its advantages, with the use of absolute values of reference entropies, as prescribed by Millero and available in all thermodynamic tables.”

Similarly, I recall at the beginning of the conclusion:

“I have shown that several problems unfortunately prevent the direct use of the ‘relative’ entropy formulation considered by Millero in 1976 and 1983. In particular, this Millero’s ‘relative’ entropy formulation did not really take into account the absolute values of entropies and has never been considered since then, and in particular in IAPWS and TEOS10 formulations. For these reasons, I have based the present approach on the more modern formulation of TEOS10, with the sole addition of the absolute seawater entropy increment $\Delta\eta_s$ given by (18) proportional to both $\eta_{w0} - \eta_{s0}$ and $S_A - S_{S0}$, with the numerical value given by (20).”

I thought these two sentences summarized and explained the essence of my approach described in the theoretical Part 1 of the paper.

I hope that the new content in Section 3.1 and the new Figures 1 will be more convincing than previous versions in explaining why it was indeed needed and appropriate to replace the Millero adjustments with those of TEOS10 for general dependencies of $\eta_{sw}(t, S_A, p)$ on the temperature, salinity and pressure, on the one hand, and the need to add the increment $\Delta\eta_s(S_A)$ due to the third law of thermodynamics applied to the liquid-water and the sea-salt reference entropies, on the other hand.

In its current form, the paper is largely incomprehensible to the general reader, and even an expert physical chemist may struggle to follow the argument. I personally find the derivations difficult to understand. A clearer exposition would be essential if the author wishes to convince readers that the proposed approach is both correct and meaningful.

I have included close to the end of the introduction and at the beginning of the conclusion the following sentences:

“I show that several problems unfortunately prevent the use of the ‘relative’ entropy formulation considered by Millero in 1976 and 1983. Moreover, this ‘relative’ entropy formulation did not really take into account the absolute values of entropies and has never been used since then. This therefore justifies basing the present approach on the more modern formulation of TEOS10, with the sole addition of taking into account the absolute values of the reference entropies for liquid water and ocean salts.”

“I have shown that several problems unfortunately prevent the direct use of the ‘relative’ entropy formulation considered by Millero in 1976 and 1983. In particular, this Millero’s ‘relative’ entropy formulation did not really take into account the absolute values of entropies and has never been considered since then, and in particular in IAPWS and TEOS10 formulations.”

I believe that the main value of the absolute definition of seawater entropy lies in the new isentropic regions highlighted in the second part of the paper by using observed and analyzed datasets. These new isentropic regions cannot be identified with the current standard version of TEOS10.

I think the second part of my paper is easy to understand, with a brief reminder of the theory, which is essentially the equation for the increment to be added to the standard entropy from

TEOS10 to obtain the absolute entropy of seawater:

$$\eta_{\text{abs}} = \eta_{\text{std/TEOS10}} + \Delta\eta_s, \quad \Delta\eta_s = (\eta_{s0} - \eta_{w0}) \times \frac{(S_A - S_{SO})}{1000},$$

$$\eta_{w0} \approx 3513.4 \pm 1.7 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ (at } 0^\circ\text{C)}, \quad \eta_{s0} \approx 1633.3 \pm 15 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ (at } 0^\circ\text{C)},$$

$$\Delta\eta_s \approx (-1880 \pm 17) \times \frac{(S_A - S_{SO})}{1000}.$$

I don't think it could be any shorter or simpler, and I hope that the beautiful numerical applications shown in Part 2 will convince many general readers without them needing to know all the details of the theoretical calculations behind this increment.

On the other hand, it is true that the first theoretical part of my paper is more difficult to understand and is intended for readers who are well-versed in the complexities of thermodynamics of electrolytic solutions... that is to say, very few people, indeed. I readily admit that the general reader may not understand everything of this first part. But this is the case with many theoretical papers, whether on thermodynamics, radiation, or the chemistry of the atmosphere and oceans.

For my part, I have had to accept—without being able to redo all the calculations—the validity of the radiation schemes used in the GCM and NWP atmospheric models that I have used for over 30 years with the ARPEGE-IFS and AROME models. I think that this is what most people do when they plot quantities such as enthalpy, entropy, or potential temperature based on the IAPWS, TEOS10 or other formulations, without necessarily knowing whether the standard or other versions of them are suitable or could be improved.

Other additional General Comments

In fact, I could have chosen not to cite Frank J. Millero's two papers from 1976 (co-authored with Wing H. Leung) and 1983 (written alone), papers that are almost identical but in which a few differences, additions, and/or typos mean they are not 100 % identical.

The real story is that Rainer Feistel first contacted me in February 2014 after reading the arXiv version of my 2011 QJRMS paper on the definition of the absolute entropy of the atmosphere. He wanted to point out to me the existence of somewhat similar work by IAPWS (later TEOS10) on atmospheric thermodynamics, in which, however, the reference values derived from the third law were not taken into account.

Initially, Rainer Feistel had expressed interest in me providing them the absolute reference values for the entropies and enthalpies of the four main atmospheric gases, namely N₂, O₂, Ar, CO₂, and H₂O. The goal would have been precisely to do what I have described in Part-1, namely to replace the standard reference values with their absolute version in IAPWS and TEOS10, where they are arbitrarily set to zero. Rainer Feistel also readily accepted the possibility of calculating the absolute values for solids (H₂O ice, CO₂ ice, etc.), at least theoretically, as written in several of his papers.

Unfortunately, I was only able to complete all of these calculations starting in 2020, once I had patiently collected the latent heats and $c_p(T)$ data for all solid phases of N₂, O₂, Ar, CO₂, and H₂O. But in the meantime, Rainer Feistel was no longer at all willing to take my data into account, arguing that these absolute values were of no use in calculating the ocean's thermodynamic data. However, I had noticed that the absolute value of the entropy of dry air, as determined by Eric W. Lemmon, was already included in a commented-out line in the TEOS10 software. Accordingly, I never received a response from Rainer Feistel or Eric W. Lemmon explaining why that line remained commented out

and not activated in TEOS10, or why the absolute value for water ice mentioned in Rainer Feistel’s papers was neither coded nor activated.

Similarly, I quickly became aware of and read 1979 and 1983 Millero’s papers, but I received no response to my numerous attempts to contact Frank J. Millero to find out why his work was not included, even in part, in TEOS10. I can therefore assure the referee that I have sought to collaborate with the oceanography community on numerous occasions since 2014, particularly with Rainer Feistel, Frank J. Millero, and Rémi Tailleux, but I have been met with their obstinate and repeated refusal to collaborate on any project, whether theoretical (as in the present first part of the paper) or involving numerical applications (as in the present second part of the paper).

It was therefore simply out of scientific integrity that I gave due credit to Frank J. Millero’s 1976 and 1983 papers, despite their shortcomings, because of his pioneering attempt to account for the absolute entropies of liquid water and sea salts for the first time, even though this formulation has never been adopted since. It was also after analyzing all the issues raised in these articles that I decided to focus solely on the aspect of “absolute values of reference entropies” (though updated using more recent thermodynamic data) and to prefer the TEOS10 formulation for the remaining “nonlinear dependencies on temperature, salinity, and pressure.”

I didn’t think that this approach could, so to speak, backfire on me, leading to criticism that I had not adequately explained why it was appropriate not to adopt Frank J. Millero’s original formulation in its entirety, how my proposal differs from it, and how I could justify deviating from the work of a renowned scholar like Frank J. Millero.

The fact is that Frank J. Millero has never explained (since the 2000s) why the IAPWS and TEOS10 guidelines, which he helped develop and co-authored, differed so significantly from his recommendations from 1976 to 1983. I would like to point out, however, that Rainer Feistel had already raised numerous criticisms in 1993 regarding the earlier formulations known as “EOS80,” which included Frank J. Miller’s articles from the 1970s and 1980s, including those of 1976 and 1983.

I have made a modification to the explanation of the term $\mu_s^0(T, P)$ in equation (2), which has no impact on the subsequent calculations. Indeed, it was necessary to remove the factor N_A / M_s in the definition $\mu_s^0(T, P) = \sum_a X_a \mu_a^0(T, P)$, where $\mu_a^0(T, P)$ is defined in (2) as specific mass quantity and not, as in Feistel and Hagen (1995), as a quantity ‘per molecule.’ In doing so, I have simply brought this into line with what I had already done for the liquid water part. However, once again, this only concerns the ‘historical documentation’ section and has no impact whatsoever on the final formulation or the documentation for TEOS10.

I have also made some minor changes in section 3.3 concerning the numerical evaluations of latent heats and saturation pressure as a function of absolute entropies for ice and water vapor. The results are more accurate (with narrower uncertainty intervals) and remain consistent with the third law of thermodynamics, while providing a new physical justification for the residual entropy of water.

Best regards,

Dr.Hab. Pascal Marquet

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